

Guidelines	Year	Target region	Authorising Body	Focus	Target Population	Language
Case definitions, diagnostic algorithms, and priorities in Encephalitis: Consensus statement of the International Encephalitis Consortium (IEC)	2013	US/Global	International Encephalitis Consortium (IEC)	Viral encephalitis	A, P	English
Viral meningoencephalitis: a review of diagnostic methods and guidelines for management (EFNS)	2010	Europe	European Federation of Neurological Societies (EFNS)	Viral meningoencephalitis	U	English
Akut infektøus encefalitis(DNS)	2017	Denmark	Dansk Neurologisk Selskab (DNS)	Viral encephalitis	U	Danish
Virale Meningoenzephalitis (DGN)	2018	Germany	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Neurologie (DGN)	Viral meningoencephalitis	U	German
The Management of Encephalitis: Clinical Practice Guidelines by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA)	2008	US/Global	Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA)	Viral encephalitis	A,P	English
UK Standards for Microbiology Investigations: Investigation of Viral Encephalitis (PHE:VE)	2014	UK	Public Health England (PHE)	Viral encephalitis	U	English
Management of suspected viral encephalitis in adults (BIA/ABN)	2012	UK	British Infection Association (BIA), Association of British Neurologists (ABN)	Viral encephalitis	A	English
Management of suspected viral encephalitis in children (BIA/ABN/BPAIIG)	2012	UK	BIA, ABN, British Paediatric Allergy Immunity and Infection Group (BPAIIG)	Viral encephalitis	P (<16 yo)	English
Encefalitis (AEPED)	2011	Spain	Asociación Española de Pediatría (AEPED)	Viral encephalitis	P	Spanish
Guidelines on the management of infectious encephalitis in adults (SPILF)	2017	France	Société de Pathologie Infectieuse de Langue Française (SPILF)	Infectious encephalitis	A	English (French)
Veileder I Akuttneurologi: Infeksjoner/NevroNEL (NNF)	2017	Norway	Norsk Neurologisk Forening (NNF)	Infectious encephalitis	U	Norwegian
UK Standards for Microbiology Investigations: Meningoencephalitis (PHE:ME)	2014	United Kingdom	Public Health England (PHE)	Infectious meningoencephalitis	U	English
EFNS guideline on the management of community-acquired bacterial meningitis: report on an EFNS Task Force on acute bacterial meningitis in older children and adults (EFNS)	2008 (rev. 2010)	Europe	European Federation of Neurological Societies (EFNS)	Bacterial meningitis	A, P (older children)	English
Diagnosis and treatment of acute bacterial meningitis (ESCMID)	2016	Europe	European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ESCMID)	Bacterial meningitis	A, P	English
Rekommandationer for initial behandling af akut bakteriel meningitis hos voksne (DSI)	2018	Denmark	Dansk Selskab for Infektionsmedicin (DSI)	Bacterial meningitis	A	Danish
Practice guidelines for acute bacterial meningitis (except newborn and nosocomial meningitis)(SPILF)	2008	France	Société de Pathologie Infectieuse de Langue Française (SPILF)	Bacterial meningitis	A, P	English (French)
Ambulant erworbene bakterielle (eitrige) Meningoenzephalitis im Erwachsenenalter (DGN:BM)	2018	Germany	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Neurologie (DGN)	Bacterial meningitis	A	German
Guidelines for the early clinical and public health management of bacterial meningitis (including Meningococcal Disease) (HPSC)	2016	Ireland	Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC)	Bacterial meningitis	A, P	English
Bacteriële Meningitis (NVN)	2013	Netherlands	Nederlandse Vereniging voor Neurologie (NVN)	Bacterial meningitis	A, P	Dutch
Clinical Practice Guideline on the Management of Invasive Meningococcal Disease (MHSSE)	2013	Spain	Ministry of Health, Social Services and Equality (MHSSE)	Meningococcal Disease	P	English, Spanish